

Supplementary Table 1. Statistical analysis of the difference in relative growth rates between treatment groups in Growth Trials.

Treatment_Group 1	Vs. Treatment_Group 2	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P value
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP 500 + H9 500	-0.041	-0.076	-0.007	0.021
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 500	0.032	0.001	0.062	0.041
H9GFP 50T + H9 50	H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	0.033	0.000	0.067	0.050
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	-0.029	-0.060	0.002	0.068
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 500	0.024	-0.008	0.055	0.129
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 500	0.019	-0.008	0.046	0.159
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.021	-0.009	0.051	0.163
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	-0.021	-0.052	0.011	0.178
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 50	0.022	-0.017	0.062	0.253
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 50	-0.019	-0.059	0.020	0.316
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	0.013	-0.018	0.043	0.387
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.013	-0.019	0.044	0.398
H9GFP mock + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	-0.011	-0.038	0.016	0.410
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 50	0.014	-0.025	0.054	0.457
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.010	-0.041	0.021	0.510
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.008	-0.019	0.035	0.534
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 50	0.010	-0.028	0.047	0.598
H9GFP mock + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 500	0.009	-0.028	0.047	0.603
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP 500 + H9 500	-0.008	-0.042	0.026	0.629
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	0.005	-0.027	0.036	0.756
H9GFP mock + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	-0.001	-0.039	0.036	0.937

Supplementary Table 2. Statistical analysis of the difference in relative growth rates between treatment groups in Differentiation Trials.

Treatment_Group 1	Vs. Treatment_Group 2	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P value
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.055	-0.097	-0.012	0.015
H9GFP mock + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.046	0.009	0.082	0.017
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.050	-0.093	-0.008	0.023
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP 500 + H9 500	-0.048	-0.091	-0.005	0.030
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.040	0.002	0.077	0.039
H9GFP mock + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.045	-0.088	-0.002	0.041
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP 500 + H9 500	-0.044	-0.087	-0.001	0.045
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 50	0.039	-0.004	0.082	0.076
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.032	-0.069	0.004	0.082
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	0.026	-0.011	0.063	0.165
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	-0.022	-0.065	0.020	0.287
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	-0.018	-0.061	0.024	0.387
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.014	-0.023	0.050	0.443
H9GFP 500 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 50	0.013	-0.030	0.055	0.542
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 50	-0.010	-0.056	0.036	0.665
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	-0.009	-0.051	0.034	0.673
H9GFP 500 + H9 500	H9GFP mock + H9 500	-0.006	-0.044	0.032	0.739
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 50	-0.005	-0.051	0.040	0.809
H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	-0.005	-0.047	0.038	0.828
H9GFP 50 + H9 50	H9GFP 50 + H9 mock	-0.004	-0.050	0.042	0.848
H9GFP mock + H9 50	H9GFP mock + H9 mock	0.001	-0.042	0.043	0.965